

SULPHONAMIDES. PART I.

BY GURCHARAN LAL JUNEJA, KARTAR SINGH NARANG
AND JNANENDRA NATH RAY.

Some of 5-, 6- and 8- sulphonamidoquinolines have been synthesised. Some of the compounds have been tested on mice infected with pneumococci and encouraging results have been obtained.

M. B. 693 has found an extensive use in medicine and has proved very efficacious in the treatment of certain infectious diseases, particularly in the treatment of pneumonia. This drug contains *p*-aminobenzene-sulphonylamino group attached to a pyridine ring. It was thought interesting to synthesise compounds the type (I), because such a side-chain is known to lower toxicity.

The group, R(CH₂)_nCONH - C₆H₄SO₂NH₂, has been introduced in 5, 6 or 8 position of the quinoline molecule. (*cf.* Bobranski, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1939, 277, 75)

For this purpose *p* acetylamino benzenesulphonyl chloride has been condensed with aminoquinolines. For example, with 6-aminoquinoline it gives 6-(*p*-acetylamino benzenesulphonamido-) quinoline (II, R = COMe), which

has been hydrolysed to the related amine (II, R=H). The chloroacetyl derivative (II, R=CO·CH₂Cl) of which, when condensed with diethylamine or piperidine, gives the desired compounds of the general formula (I).

Some of these compounds have been tested on mice infected with pneumococci III and have given results which compare very favourably with M.B. 693. These details will be published elsewhere.

EXPERIMENTAL.

6 (p-Acetylaminobenzenesulphonamido)-quinoline.—A solution of 6-aminoquinoline (0.52 g.) and *p*-acetylaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride (0.46 g.) in dry chloroform (75 c.c.) was heated on a steam-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, when a brownish yellow product separated out. Chloroform was decanted off and the residue, after trituration with water, was crystallised from alcohol (animal charcoal; in colourless transparent plates, m.p. 283°, yield 0.5 g. (Bobranski records m. p. 282°). (Found: N, 12.04. C₁₇H₁₅O₂N₂S requires N, 12.3 per cent).

6 p-Aminobenzenesulphonamidoquinoline (II, R=H).—A mixture of the foregoing acetyl amino compound (0.5 g.) and hydrochloric acid (10 c.c., *d* 1.15) was refluxed on the steam-bath for 10 minutes. The cooled solution was basified with ammonia when the amine was obtained as a pale yellow product. This was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 200°, yield theoretical. (Bobranski records m. p. 201°) (Found. N, 13.42. C₁₅H₁₃O₂N₂S requires N, 14.0 per cent).

6-p-Chloroacetylaminobenzenesulphonamidoquinoline (II, R=COCH₂Cl).—Chloroacetyl chloride (1.2 g.) was gradually added to a solution of the amine (3 g.) in dry dioxan (50 c.c.). The mixture was warmed to 70° for 2 minutes and then allowed to cool. The solvent was decanted off and the pale yellow residue washed with a small amount of ice-cold water and then crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless small plates, m.p. 166-68° (decomp.). (Found after drying in high vacuum at 120°: N, 10.0. C₁₇H₁₄O₂N₂SCl·HCl requires N, 10.19 per cent).

6 p-Piperidinoacetylaminobenzenesulphonamidoquinoline.—A solution of the above substance (4.1 g.) and piperidine (1.7 g.) in absolute alcohol (150 c.c.) was refluxed on the steam-bath for 2½ hours. After removal of the solvent the residue was treated with water when a slight turbidity appeared. Sodium acetate was added to the filtrate and the base extracted with ethyl acetate. The crude base obtained after removal of the solvent solidified on repeated treatment with hot petroleum ether. The substance was finally crystallised from a mixture of benzene and ethyl

acetate (2 : 1) in colourless plates, m.p. 131°. (Found : N, 13'46. $C_{22}H_{24}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 13'21 per cent).

6-(*p*-Diethylaminoacetylaminobenzenesulphonamido)-quinoline, prepared in the same manner as the above piperidino compound, crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (1 : 10) in colourless plates, m.p. 137°. (Found : N, 13'13. $C_{21}H_{24}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 13'52 per cent).

6-Substituted derivatives (with $n=2$) as well as all the 8- and 5- substituted compounds described below were prepared in the same way as the corresponding 6-substituted derivatives ($n=1$) which have already been described. 6-(*p*-Chloropropionylaminobenzenesulphonamido)-quinoline hydrochloride crystallised from acetic acid in light yellow transparent needles. (Found : N, 9'43. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3NSCl \cdot HCl$ requires N, 9'82 per cent).

6-(*p*-Piperidinopropionylaminobenzenesulphonamido)-quinoline, obtained in 60% yield, crystallised from benzene, m.p. 198-201°. (Found : N, 12'9. $C_{23}H_{26}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 12'78 per cent).

6-(*p*-Diethylaminopropionylaminobenzenesulphonamido)-quinoline was obtained in 80% yield. It crystallised from benzene in colourless plates, m.p. 147-49°. (Found : N, 13'18. $C_{22}H_{26}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 13'15 per cent).

8-(*p*-Acetylaminobenzenesulphonamido)-quinoline crystallised from alcohol in transparent rods, m.p. 194°, yield 70%. (Bobranski records m. p. 193°). (Found : N, 12'21. $C_{17}H_{15}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 12'31 per cent).

The amine from the above compound crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 188°, yield quantitative. (Bobranski records m. p. 193'5). (Found : N, 13'56. $C_{15}H_{15}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 14'0 per cent).

8-(*p*-Chloroacetylaminobenzenesulphonamido)-quinoline hydrochloride, obtained in 55% yield, crystallised from glacial acetic acid in pale yellow transparent plates, m.p. 220° (decomp.). (Found : N, 10'29. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3N_3S \cdot HCl$ requires N, 10'19 per cent).

8-(*p*-Piperidinoacetylaminobenzenesulphonamido)-quinoline, obtained in theoretical yield, was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether in colourless plates, m.p. 172-73°. (Found : N, 13'53. $C_{23}H_{24}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 13'2 per cent).

8-(*p*-Diethylaminoacetylaminobenzenesulphonamido)-quinoline, obtained in 70% yield, crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether in colourless plates, m.p. 115-16°. (Found : N, 13'19. $C_{24}H_{24}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 13'59 per cent).

8-(*p*-Chloropropionylaminobenzenesulphonamido)-quinoline hydrochloride crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless transparent

prisms, m.p. 228° (decomp.). (Found : N, 10'23. $C_{15}H_{16}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 9'86 per cent).

8-(p-Piperidinopropionylaminobenzenesulphonamido)-quinoline, obtained in quantitative yield, crystallised from benzene in colourless plates, m.p. 178°. (Found : N, 12'9. $C_{23}H_{26}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 12'78 per cent).

8-(p-Diethylaminopropionylaminobenzenesulphonamido)-quinoline, obtained in quantitative yield, crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether in colourless rectangular prisms, m.p. 95-96°. (Found N, 12'7. $C_{22}H_{26}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 13'14 per cent).

5-(p-Acetylamino benzenesulphonamido)-quinoline, obtained in 60% yield, crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in colourless needles, m.p. 254° (decomp.). (Bobranski records m.p. 257-58° decomp). (Found : N, 12'68. $C_{17}H_{18}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 12'32 per cent). The acetyl derivative on hydrolysis gave the amine in a theoretical yield. The amine crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless rods, m.p. 226-28°. (Bobranski records m. p. 230°). (Found : N, 14'16. $C_{15}H_{13}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 14'05 per cent). The hydrochloride of the chloroacetyl derivative of the amine, obtained in theoretical yield, was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow plates, m.p. 226°. (Found after drying in high vacuum at 130° : N, 9'89. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 10'19 per cent).

5-(p-Piperidinoacetylaminobenzenesulphonamido)-quinoline crystallised from benzene in small plates, m.p. 217-18°. (Found : N, 13'09. $C_{22}H_{26}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 13'2 per cent).

The compounds were tested for antipneumococcal activity on mice infected with type III pneumococci against M.B. 693 as control and very encouraging results were obtained in some cases, details of which will be published elsewhere with other authors.